

**Virtual Reality Interventions for Autism Spectrum Disorder: A Meta-Analysis of Efficacy and
Evidence-Based Design Guidelines**

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Abstract

This meta-analysis systematically evaluated the efficacy of virtual reality (VR) interventions in improving multidimensional abilities among individuals with autism spectrum disorder (ASD). Following PRISMA guidelines, we synthesized data from 20 randomized controlled trials (n=918 participants) across five databases. A random-effects model using Hedges' g was employed to quantify effect sizes, with subgroup analyses exploring moderators. Results demonstrated significant medium-to-large improvements across domains: cognitive function [$g = 0.73$; 95% CI (0.09, 1.38); $p < 0.05$; $I^2 = 75\%$], social skills [$g = 0.73$; 95% CI (0.41, 1.05); $p < 0.01$; $I^2 = 56.1\%$], daily living skills [$g = 0.76$; 95% CI (0.09, 1.42); $p < 0.05$; $I^2 = 74.73\%$], affective skills [$g = 0.63$; 95% CI (0.03, 1.23); $p < 0.05$; $I^2 = 82\%$], and overall functioning [$g = 1.12$; 95% CI (0.45, 1.79); $p < 0.05$; $I^2 = 25\%$]. Immersive devices yielded larger social skill gains compared to non-immersive systems, while interventions ≤ 30 minutes/session and ≤ 3 sessions/week showed superior efficacy. No significant publication bias was detected via Egger's test ($p > 0.05$). We recommend integrating VR as an adjunctive therapeutic tool, particularly using immersive protocols for early social skill intervention. Future research should prioritize longitudinal designs, standardized outcome measures, and expanded inclusion of underrepresented subgroups (e.g., female patients, patients with multiple comorbidities, etc.).

Keywords: Virtual reality technology; Autism spectrum disorder; Meta-analysis; Developmental Disabilities; Technology-Based Intervention

1. Introduction

Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is a complex neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by impairments in social communication and social interaction, along with restricted and repetitive patterns of behavior, interest, or activities ([American Psychiatric Association, 2013](#)). Statistics from the US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention have shown a marked rise in the prevalence of ASD diagnoses in recent decades, with 1 in 77 children currently being diagnosed ([Pain et al., 2019](#)). ASD imposes substantial socioeconomic burdens across the lifespan, characterized by pervasive functional impairments in occupational participation and independent living capacities among affected individuals. Longitudinal studies indicate that fewer than 60% of adults with ASD achieve full-time employment or residential autonomy, necessitating prolonged familial and institutional support systems into adulthood ([Marriage et al., 2009](#)). These challenges are compounded by high rates of psychiatric comorbidities (e.g., anxiety, depression) and persistent deficits in adaptive functioning, which collectively exacerbate caregiver strain and societal healthcare expenditures ([Giolo et al., 2023](#)). By 2025, the annual direct medical, non-medical, and productivity costs associated with ASD in the United States are projected to reach \$500 billion ([Masi et al., 2017](#)). Numerous factors may contribute to the development of ASD, including genetic predispositions, parental mental health disorders, and prenatal exposure to psychiatric medications.

A range of evidence-based intervention strategies have been developed for children with ASD, including behavioral therapy ([Makrygianni et al., 2018](#)), the Treatment and Education of Autistic and Related Communication-Handicapped Children (TEACCH) program ([Sanz-Cervera et al., 2018](#)), the Picture Exchange Communication System (PECS) ([Bondy & Frost, 1994](#)) ration therapy, music therapy, speech therapy, and homeopathy, among others. In clinical practice, a comprehensive treatment approach, which

includes pharmacological intervention, behavioral correction, educational training, and physical therapy, is commonly employed. While early diagnosis and intervention may enhance rehabilitation outcomes, the limitations of traditional approaches have become increasingly apparent. Specifically, the high financial costs impose substantial burdens on families, compounded by significant geographical disparities in service accessibility. Moreover, the standardized protocols of conventional methods often fail to address the neurodevelopmental heterogeneity of ASD populations, with varying symptom profiles and treatment responses potentially undermining intervention effectiveness (Lord et al., 2022). Therefore, there is an urgent need to explore cost-effective, accessible treatment methods that are tailored to individual neurodevelopmental characteristics to address the limitations of traditional interventions.

In recent years, technological interventions have emerged as a promising approach to addressing the core challenges of ASD (Grynszpan et al., 2014), particularly in overcoming social communication deficits and adaptive behavioral limitations. Notably, VR technology, ranging from non-immersive desktop systems to fully immersive devices such as head-mounted displays (HMDs) and cave automatic virtual environment (CAVE) systems, has demonstrated unique therapeutic potential by creating interactive, immersive 3D environments (Munson & Pasqual, 2012). Despite the significant deficits in communication and social skills exhibited by individuals with ASD, such as shyness, communication barriers, and anxiety in informal social settings, they show a strong interest in technology. Furthermore, integrating technological methods into the behavioral therapy of ASD patients not only effectively enhances treatment outcomes but also offers considerable benefits in terms of economic cost. Research has further shown that individuals with ASD are more sensitive to visual stimuli than to other types of sensory inputs. These findings have contributed to the widespread application of technology in digital behavioral therapy (Meadan et al., 2011). Importantly, the

modular design of VR platforms allows integration with biometric monitoring technologies (e.g., eye-tracking, galvanic skin response sensors), enabling real-time adaptation of therapeutic scenarios based on user-specific stress markers or attention patterns. These technological synergisms not only enhance intervention personalization but also present scalable solutions to traditional behavioral therapy's limitations in ecological validity and implementation costs.

Despite existing studies confirming that VR technology can aid in the rehabilitation of ASD patients, controversies persist regarding its effectiveness in terms of specific outcome measures, and its therapeutic effects are not always as pronounced as expected. Additionally, issues related to VR as a novel therapeutic method, including concerns about patient safety and control over the duration, frequency, and intervention period, remain unresolved. Hence, there is an urgent need for greater attention to meta-analyses of randomized controlled trials (RCTs) to rigorously assess the effect of VR-based treatments on individuals with autism. These findings enhance our understanding of the therapeutic benefits of VR interventions in the treatment of ASD. Given the above, our specific aims included: (1) systematically and comprehensively evaluating the effects of VR interventions on ASD, (2) to explore potential moderating factors, guiding clinical practice, and (3) to evaluate the potential adverse effects of VR interventions on ASD.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Registration of Systematic Review Protocol

This systematic review and meta-analysis was conducted following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) guidelines (Page et al., 2021), and registered in

the PROSPERO database (CRD42024581544).

2.2. Search strategy

The literature search and selection adhered to the PRISMA criteria and guidelines and involved a thorough investigation across five databases: Web of Science, PubMed, EMBASE, the Cochrane Library, and CNKI. The search spanned from database establishment to August 20, 2024. Clinical randomized controlled trials on the use of VR technology in patients with ASD were included. The search terms included “Virtual training” OR “Virtual environment” OR “Virtual Reality” OR “Educational Virtual Realities” OR “Educational Virtual Reality” OR “Educational Virtual” OR “Virtual Realities” AND “Autistic Spectrum Disorder” OR “Autistic Spectrum” OR “Autism Spectrum Disorders” OR “ASD” OR “Autism”. We used a combination of subject headings and free text, with no language or publication type restrictions for the literature search. An example of the literature search strategy using the PubMed database ("Virtual Reality"[Mesh] OR ("reality virtual" OR "virtual reality educational" OR "Educational Virtual Realities" OR "Educational Virtual Reality" OR "virtual reality instructional" OR "virtual environment" OR "Virtual Reality" OR "VR" OR "game based virtual reality" OR "computer based virtual reality")) AND ("Autism Spectrum Disorder"[Mesh] OR ("Autistic Spectrum Disorder" OR "disorder autistic spectrum" OR "Autism Spectrum Disorders" OR "ASD" OR "Autism")). All database search strategies are shown in Table S1.

2.3. Eligibility criteria

The eligibility of the studies for inclusion was independently assessed by two authors (DG and QY), and the final decision of the included studies was made after a summary of the comments was prepared and discussed with a third author (JW). The reference lists of all included studies were examined

during the secondary search.

The literature screening was based on the PICOS criteria for evidence-based medicine, and the specific literature inclusion criteria were as follows: (1) Study participants were individuals who met the diagnostic criteria for Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) as defined in the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fourth Edition (DSM-IV) or Fifth Edition (DSM-V), or had received clinical confirmation of ASD diagnosis. (2) The intervention in the experimental group was the use of VR technology, whereas the control group received conventional rehabilitation training or a blank control. (3) The study design should be an RCT. We excluded studies if (1) Not utilize VR technology for treatment. (2) Nonrandomized controlled trials. (3) Reviews, conference proceedings, and animal studies. (4) The aim of the study was not to investigate the therapeutic effect of VR technology on patients with ASD. (5) Studies with incomplete outcome reporting.

2.4. Data extraction

Two authors (DG and QY) conducted the initial extraction of relevant data, with a third author serving as an additional check (JW). A systematic data extraction form was employed to record pertinent information from each article, including (1) the first author and year of publication; (2) sample characteristics (e.g., sample size, mean age of participants); (3) details of the interventions (e.g., type of VR, duration, frequency and period of intervention); and (4) measurement tools and outcome indicators.

2.5. Risk of bias assessment

A quality appraisal of each study was conducted independently by two study authors (DG and QY) using the Cochrane 'Risk of bias 2' (RoB 2) tool (Sterne et al., 2019) and disagreements were resolved with JW. Based on the criteria from the Rob 2 tool, studies were categorised as being at low risk

of bias, high risk of bias and having some concerns. The assessments were conducted for five individual domains: bias arising from the randomisation process, bias due to deviations from intended interventions, bias due to missing outcome data, bias in measurement of the outcome, bias in selection of the reported result and an overall bias.

2.6. Statistical analysis

For descriptive statistics, we used the standardized mean difference (with the standard deviation, SD) as a measure of central tendency. Hedges' g method was used to estimate the standardized mean difference (SMD). The sizes of Hedges' g effects can be categorized into small effects ($g = 0.2$), medium effects ($g = 0.5$), and large effects ($g = 0.8$). Given the heterogeneity caused by study differences (e.g., demographics or VR protocol), a random effects model was employed for the meta-analysis. This approach was selected over the fixed-effects model because of its capacity to account for the variability of true effect sizes and its suitability for included studies (Dettori et al., 2022).

We used Cochran's Q statistic to determine heterogeneity; additionally, τ^2 was calculated to quantify the variance between studies, and I^2 was employed to evaluate the percentage of variance attributed to between-study heterogeneity. The size of I^2 was classified as low ($I^2 < 25\%$), moderate ($25\% < I^2 < 75\%$), or high ($I^2 > 75\%$). Forest plots were designed to report the results of the meta-analysis.

Sensitivity analyses were developed to detect outliers or influential cases via leave-one-out methods for data analysis. If a study was detected as an outlier or influential case, it was removed from the meta-analysis. Publication bias was assessed through the inspection of contour-enhanced funnel plots and Egger's bias tests (Egger et al., 1997). In instances of significant bias, Duval and Tweedie's trim-and-fill method was applied (Duval & Tweedie, 2000), alongside the calculation of the number of unpublished

studies needed to negate the observed effect ($p > 0.05$).

Subgroup analyses were conducted to investigate the influence of several factors, including the age, degree of device immersion, intervention time, intervention frequency, and intervention period.

The “rma” “forest,” “baujat,” “fitstats” and “regplot” functions from the “metafor” package were employed to perform the meta-analysis (Viechtbauer, 2010). All analyses were conducted via R studio (R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria).

3. Results

3.1. Study selection

The literature selection process is shown in Figure 1. A total of 1,856 articles were retrieved from databases including PubMed, Embase, Web of Science, the Cochrane Library, and CNKI. After excluding 503 duplicates, 1,240 articles were removed based on title and abstract screening. Thirteen full-text articles could not be accessed, while 93 full-text articles were downloaded. Of these, 1 article was excluded due to incompatible outcome measures, 21 were review articles, 11 could not provide extractable data, and 40 had incompatible study designs. Ultimately, 20 articles were included in the analysis.

*** Fig. 1. Near Here***

3.2. Study characteristics

A total of 918 participants across 34 studies from 20 articles were included, with 460 participants assigned to the VR intervention group and 431 assigned to the control group. The studies explored the effects of VR on various skills, including social skills ($n = 11$) (Ambrose, 2022; Frolli et al., 2022; He et al., 2021; Ip et al., 2018; Maskey et al., 2019; Sosnowski et al., 2022; Wu, 2023; X. Zhang & Zhao, 2022; J. Zhao et al., 2022; J. Zhao & Zhang, 2021; S. Zhao, 2022), affective skills ($n = 9$) (Frolli et al., 2022; Ip

et al., 2018; Maskey et al., 2019; Sepehri Bonab et al., 2024; Sosnowski et al., 2022; Sun, 2019; White et al., 2016; Wu, 2023; J. Zhao & Zhang, 2021), daily life skills (n = 6) (Genova et al., 2021, 2024; Smith et al., 2014, 2021; J. Zhao & Zhang, 2021; S. Zhao, 2022), cognitive abilities (n = 5) (Sepehri Bonab et al., 2024; Smith et al., 2021; J. Zhao et al., 2022; J. Zhao & Zhang, 2021; S. Zhao, 2022), and overall improvement effects (n = 3) (Y. Wang et al., 2016; J. Zhao & Zhang, 2021; S. Zhao, 2022). The participants ranged in age from 3-31 years, with the primary age group being 3-12 years, with a focus on early interventions for preschool children. The participants were from China, the United States, the United Kingdom, and Italy, with a significantly greater proportion of boys than girls (ranging from 4:1-5:1), which aligns with the typical gender distribution in ASD. In the intervention group, 13 studies used VR technology alone, whereas 7 studies combined VR with other therapies. Most of the studies had an intervention period of 10-24 weeks, with 2-3 sessions per week, each lasting 15-45 minutes. The detailed characteristics of the studies are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Near Here

3.3. Risk of bias within studies

The risk of bias ratings for each study are provided in Supplementary file (Fig. S1). Specifically, 2 studies (X. Zhang & Zhao, 2022; J. Zhao et al., 2022) were found to exhibit a high risk of bias in the randomization process, suggesting a potential limitation. Moreover, 2 studies (Wu, 2023; S. Zhao, 2022) revealed missing outcome data, which could impact the overall robustness of their results. In three studies (Sosnowski et al., 2022; Y. Wang et al., 2016; S. Zhao, 2022), the risk of bias across most assessment areas remained unclear. Regarding measurement bias, all studies were low risk or unclear. Regarding the selection of outcomes to report, one study (J. Zhao & Zhang, 2021) was rated as high risk and the

remaining studies were low risk or unclear.

3.4. Main analysis

Fig. 2. Near Here

3.4.1. Social skills

A meta-analysis indicated that VR significantly improved social skills in children with ASD compared with the control group [$g = 0.73$; 95% CI (0.41, 1.05); $p < 0.01$]. Eleven studies (Ambrose, 2022; Frolli et al., 2022; He et al., 2021; Ip et al., 2018; Maskey et al., 2019; Sosnowski et al., 2022; Wu, 2023; X. Zhang & Zhao, 2022; J. Zhao et al., 2022; J. Zhao & Zhang, 2021; S. Zhao, 2022) were included in the meta-analysis, which revealed moderate heterogeneity ($\tau^2 = 0.11$; $I^2 = 56.1\%$). The Autism Treatment Evaluation Checklist and the Autism Behavior Checklist were used to assess improvements. The intervention period ranged from 2 to 24 weeks, with sessions lasting between 7.5 and 45 minutes, and interventions occurred 2 to 7 times per week. VR-based interventions, including 3D projection or video games (Frolli et al., 2022; Sosnowski et al., 2022; X. Zhang & Zhao, 2022), head-mounted VR displays (He et al., 2021; J. Zhao et al., 2022; J. Zhao & Zhang, 2021; S. Zhao, 2022), CAVE-VR systems (Ip et al., 2018), and Blue Room VRE (Maskey et al., 2019), vary. Five studies combined VR with other therapies, such as applied behavior analysis (S. Zhao, 2022), home rehabilitation care (J. Zhao & Zhang, 2021), cognitive behavioral therapy (Maskey et al., 2019), sensory integration training (X. Zhang & Zhao, 2022; J. Zhao & Zhang, 2021), and fine motor training (J. Zhao et al., 2022).

The subgroup analyses based on the age, level of immersion, intervention duration, frequency, and period were performed. The intervention was more effective in children [$g = 0.66$; 95% CI (0.18, 1.15); $p = 0.01$] compared to adolescents [$g = 0.64$; 95% CI (-0.14, 1.44); $p = 0.08$]. The intervention

effect was better in immersive devices [$g = 0.66$; 95% CI (0.27, 1.03); $p = 0.004$] than in non-immersive devices [$g = 0.96$; 95% CI (-0.34, 2.28); $p = 0.08$]. The intervention was more effective at less than 3 times per week [$g = 0.72$; 95% CI (0.24, 1.2); $p = 0.01$] than at 3 and more times per week [$g = 0.63$; 95% CI (-1.64, 2.92); $p = 0.17$]. Shorter interventions (<30 minutes) resulted in greater improvements [$g = 0.74$; 95% CI (0.26, 1.21); $p = 0.01$], while interventions lasting 30 minutes [$g = 0.52$; 95% CI (-0.13, 1.18); $p = 0.07$] or more were not significant. Interventions between 10 and 20 weeks [$g = 0.64$; 95% CI (0.18, 1.09); $p = 0.014$] are more effective than interventions under 10 weeks [$g = 0.63$; 95% CI (-1.64, 2.92); $p = 0.17$] and over 20 weeks [$g = 0.72$; 95% CI (-6.02, 7.46); $p = 0.4$]. However, no statistically significant differences were observed between subgroups ($P_m > 0.05$).

3.4.2. *Affective skills*

A meta-analysis revealed that VR interventions were more effective than control interventions in improving affective skills [$g = 0.63$; 95% CI (0.03, 1.23); $p < 0.05$]. A total of nine studies (Frolli et al., 2022; Ip et al., 2018; Maskey et al., 2019; Sepehri Bonab et al., 2024; Sosnowski et al., 2022; White et al., 2016; Wu, 2023; Yu Sun, 2019; J. Zhao & Zhang, 2021) were included, showing high heterogeneity ($\tau^2 = 0.46$; $I^2 = 82\%$). The Q test confirmed significant heterogeneity between the studies ($Q = 37.15$; $df = 8$; $p < 0.01$). The intervention period ranged from 6-24 weeks, with session lengths varying from 7.5-40 minutes and intervention frequencies ranging from 2-3 times per week. Affective skill improvement was evaluated via the PEP-3 scale, the Barkley Deficits in Executive Functioning Scale (BDEFS), and the EK-man60 scale. Four studies (Frolli et al., 2022; Sepehri Bonab et al., 2024; Sosnowski et al., 2022; White et al., 2016) used VR to simulate game scenarios for the intervention, whereas five studies employed automatic VR environments (Ip et al., 2018), head-mounted VR displays (Maskey et al., 2019;

Yu Sun, 2019; S. Zhao, 2022) and 3D projection-based VR for affective literacy interventions (J. Zhao & Zhang, 2021).

The subgroup analyses based on the age, level of immersion, intervention duration, frequency, and period were performed. The intervention was more effective in children [$g = 0.89$; 95% CI (-0.27, 2.06); $p = 0.1$] compared to adolescents [$g = 0.38$; 95% CI (-0.73, 1.51); $p = 0.35$]. However, the effects were not statistically significant in either group. Immersive devices showed a higher effect size [$g = 0.74$; 95% CI (-0.32, 1.81); $p = 0.13$] compared to non-immersive devices [$g = 0.56$; 95% CI (-0.30, 1.44); $p = 0.1$]. Neither subgroup showed significant intervention effects. Interventions lasting <30 minutes demonstrated a significant effect [$g = 0.70$; 95% CI (0.03, 1.38); $p = 0.04$], while interventions lasting ≥ 30 minutes did not [$g = 0.71$; 95% CI (-1.37, 2.8); $p = 0.35$]. Interventions performed <3 times per week showed an effect size of [$g = 0.58$; 95% CI (-0.3, 1.47); $p = 0.12$], while interventions performed ≥ 3 times per week showed a higher, but non-significant, effect size [$g = 1.07$; 95% CI (-0.59, 2.74); $p = 0.13$]. Interventions lasting <10 weeks showed a higher, but non-significant, effect size [$g = 1.24$; 95% CI (-1.63, 4.12); $p = 0.2$], compared to those lasting 10–20 weeks [$g = 0.42$; 95% CI (-0.61, 1.47); $p = 0.281$] and >20 weeks [$g = 0.35$; 95% CI (-9.55, 10.27); $p = 0.72$]. No statistically significant differences were observed between subgroups ($P_m > 0.05$).

3.4.3. Daily Life Skills

A meta-analysis revealed that VR interventions significantly improved life skills in individuals with ASD compared with the control group [$g = 0.76$; 95% CI (0.09, 1.42); $p < 0.05$]. A total of six studies (Genova et al., 2021, 2024; Smith et al., 2014, 2021; J. Zhao & Zhang, 2021; S. Zhao, 2022) were included, with moderate heterogeneity between the studies ($\tau^2 = 0.28$; $I^2 = 74.73\%$), and no significant

differences were found between them ($Q = 25.16$; $df = 5$; $p < 0.01$). The intervention period ranged from 2-24 weeks, with session lengths ranging from 20-45 minutes. Four studies employed a VR interview training system for the intervention, and the improvement effects were evaluated on the basis of performance in postintervention interviews.

The subgroup analysis results showed that age, device immersion level, intervention frequency, and period did not have a significant moderating effect.

3.4.4. *Cognitive functions*

A meta-analysis indicated that VR interventions significantly improved cognitive functions in individuals with ASD compared with the control group [$g = 0.73$; 95% CI (0.09, 1.38); $p < 0.05$]. Five studies (Ji & Yang, 2021; Sepehri Bonab et al., 2024; X. Zhang & Zhao, 2022; J. Zhao & Zhang, 2021; S. Zhao, 2022) were included, with low heterogeneity between studies ($\tau^2 = 0.2$; $I^2 = 25\%$). The Q test revealed significant heterogeneity between the studies ($Q = 14.4$; $df = 4$; $p < 0.01$). The intervention period ranged from 2-24 weeks, with session lengths ranging from 15-60 minutes, and intervention frequencies varied from 2-7 times per week. Cognitive function improvement was assessed via the PEP-3 (Liu et al., 2022) and ATEC scales. One study combined VR technology with home rehabilitation therapy (J. Zhao & Zhang, 2021), whereas four studies (Ji & Yang, 2021; Sepehri Bonab et al., 2024; X. Zhang & Zhao, 2022; S. Zhao, 2022) used VR technology alone. The immersion level of the intervention tools varied, including high-immersion devices such as head-mounted VR displays and 3D VR games, as well as low-immersion devices such as FIFA21 games.

The subgroup analysis results showed that intervention frequency, duration and period did not have a significant moderating effect.

3.4.5. Overall improvement effect

A meta-analysis revealed that VR interventions significantly outperformed the control group in terms of overall improvement for individuals with ASD [$g = 1.12$; 95% CI (0.45, 1.79); $p < 0.05$]. A total of three studies (Y. Wang et al., 2016; J. Zhao & Zhang, 2021; S. Zhao, 2022) were included, with moderate heterogeneity between the studies ($\tau^2 = 0.01$; $I^2 = 25\%$) and no significant differences between the studies ($Q = 2.55$; $df = 2$; $p > 0.05$). Overall improvement was assessed via the Childhood Autism Rating Scale. Both studies included participants aged 3 to 5 years, and interventions consisted of VR combined with either home rehabilitation therapy (J. Zhao & Zhang, 2021) or traditional behavioral training (Y. Wang et al., 2016), with an intervention period of 24 weeks and session durations ranging from 25-40 minutes.

3.5. Sensitivity analyses

Sensitivity analyses were performed using the leave-one-out method, recalculating the overall effect size for each domain (social, affective, daily life skills, and cognitive function) to assess the impact of each study on the pooled results. The sensitivity analysis revealed that the removal of any individual study did not significantly alter the pooled effect sizes, confirming the robustness of our findings. Additionally, Egger's test was conducted to assess publication bias for each domain, and no significant publication bias was detected ($p > 0.05$). The visual inspection of the funnel plot further supported the absence of bias, with no asymmetry observed (Fig. S2).

4. Discussion

4.1. Principal Findings

This study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of VR-based interventions for individuals with ASD and found that VR interventions, whether used alone or in combination with traditional rehabilitation therapies, significantly outperformed traditional rehabilitation alone. The subgroup analyses further examined the effects of device immersion, intervention duration, frequency, and period on improvements in social and affective skills. Early intervention using immersive VR devices for social skills, limited to no more than three sessions per week, each lasting 30 minutes for 10 to 20 weeks, may be more effective. Similarly, interventions for affective skills should also be limited to approximately 30 minutes per session.

4.2. Effect of VR Technology on the Improvement of Multidimensional Abilities in ASD

Individuals with ASD exhibit atypical cognitive functions, such as executive dysfunction, perceptual anomalies, impaired social cognition and perception, as well as information processing deficits, often associated with attentional deficiencies (Rommelse et al., 2011). Research shows that individuals with ASD often face challenges in attention regulation, particularly in sustaining and shifting focus. However, these deficits are not uniform; performance on selective attention tasks varies among individuals with ASD, especially when exposed to complex or social stimuli. Keehn et al. found that attentional deficits could impair the ability to process complex social stimuli, a hallmark feature of the disorder (Keehn et al., 2010). Moreover, individuals with ASD exhibit notable impairments in social cognition. According to the "Theory of Mind" model proposed by Belmonte et al., individuals with ASD often fail to understand others' emotions, intentions, and beliefs, which directly affects their social interaction and communication abilities (Belmonte, 2008). Recent studies indicate that deficits in joint and social attention further intensify social challenges in individuals with ASD. Furthermore, individuals with ASD typically experience problems with information processing speed, particularly in visual and auditory tasks.

Minshew et al. demonstrated that individuals with ASD have slower response times in simple information processing tasks, which is linked to reduced brain efficiency in processing information (Rezayi et al., 2023). This slower processing speed is believed to be due to lower cognitive efficiency, especially in tasks that require social or executive control (Minshew & Goldstein, 2001). In addition, individuals with ASD often exhibit difficulties in language expression, grammar comprehension, and pragmatic language skills (Pickles et al., 2009). Although some individuals may develop basic language skills, they often encounter substantial difficulties in understanding and using complex language. Previous studies have reported the effectiveness of VR interventions in addressing neurocognitive deficits in children with ASD (De Luca et al., 2018, 2021; Shahmoradi & Rezayi, 2022; M. Wang & Reid, 2013), which is consistent with the findings of this study. VR technology is task-oriented and, combined with highly immersive virtual environments, promotes a sense of immersion during training, enhancing attention, memory, and other cognitive functions, thereby positively influencing overall cognitive performance. From a neurological perspective, this effect may be due to the multisensory stimulation provided by VR, which reduces compensatory activation in areas like the prefrontal cortex, thereby improving cognitive efficiency and overall cognitive function (Liao et al., 2020).

A lack of social interest and motivation often results in substantial difficulties in social interactions among individuals with ASD (Neuhaus et al., 2019a). Even when some social interest is displayed, these individuals typically lack the necessary social skills, which results in difficulties in emotional communication and interaction (Ung et al., 2013). These obstacles make it difficult for individuals with ASD to form and maintain friendships (Neuhaus et al., 2019b; Yamada et al., 2020). Traditional therapeutic methods often struggle to address these issues effectively in real-world

environments, particularly when faced with uncontrollable environmental stimuli, which can trigger anxiety and withdrawal in patients. However, VR technology, by offering a controllable, immersive training environment, can effectively modulate the intensity and complexity of social stimuli, providing a risk-free platform for training. This study indicates that VR technology significantly outperforms traditional interventions in improving social skills among ASD patients. This finding is consistent with the study by (Ke et al., 2022), which revealed that VR technology, through highly realistic virtual scenarios, offers ASD patients the opportunity to gradually adapt to complex social situations, enabling them to practice social skills repeatedly without pressure from the real world. Additionally, the real-time feedback mechanism of VR helps patients correct erroneous behaviors and reinforce appropriate social interaction patterns, thereby significantly enhancing their social capabilities.

ASD patients exhibit inherent impairments and deficits, poor independent living skills and a lack of essential life competencies. VR interventions can provide a safer and more realistic training environment for these patients, mitigating real-world hazards such as crossing the street or using public transportation—scenarios that carry certain risks. By using VR technology to simulate realistic street environments, ASD patients can gradually acquire life skills within a secure setting (Cox et al., 2017). Furthermore, ASD patients face lower employment rates due to challenges in job interview situations (Penton et al., 2023). The results of this study show that VR technology significantly improves the life skills of ASD patients. Compared with the control group, patients exhibited notable improvements in interview performance following VR intervention, which is consistent with the findings of (Li et al., 2023). This may be due to the controlled stimuli, safe environment, and immersive experience, which collectively help patients more effectively with expert skills and successfully transfer the acquired abilities

to real-world situations.

Several studies suggest that VR technology can be an effective tool for training affective skills. Studies by (Silver & Oakes, 2001) and (Lacava et al., 2007) also support the effectiveness of VR in enhancing affective skills. However, discrepancies exist between studies. For example, an RCT (Frolli et al., 2022) reported no significant difference in patients' performance on primary emotional recognition tasks between traditional emotion recognition training and VR-based training. However, the VR group better recognized secondary and contextual emotions. This discrepancy may be attributed to differences in the intervention protocols and their primary objectives. The advantage of VR technology might lie not in recognizing primary emotions but in helping patients understand more complex emotions and their associations with specific contexts. This study further corroborates the advantages of VR in improving emotional recognition, particularly in more complex situations. In affective skill training, the immersive nature of VR enables patients to engage in repeated practice and contextual application within virtual scenarios, thereby enhancing their affective skills. The Childhood Autism Rating Scale assesses overall improvement, with fifteen items, including interpersonal relationships, imitation (of actions and language), body usage, and affective responses. Lower scores indicate better outcomes. The results of this study suggest that VR technology offers more effective interventions.

4.3. Factors Influencing the Effectiveness of VR Interventions in ASD

Significant differences exist in the maintenance and generalization of intervention effects across various devices. For instance, hardware such as head-mounted displays (HMDs) and VR headsets create distinct intervention environments. Fully immersive VR interventions offer more realistic virtual settings for children with ASD, which can help improve the maintenance and generalization of intervention

outcomes (Wu, 2023). For some individuals with ASD, hospital environments may induce anxiety, negatively impacting their engagement and treatment effectiveness. In contrast, home environments generally promote greater relaxation, thereby enhancing patient acceptance of treatment. Additionally, private offices and controlled laboratory settings may also influence the sustainability and generalization of intervention effects (Yingying Cao; Jianjun Chen; Dianzhen Liu 2022).

The theory of early neural plasticity suggests that 0-3 years are critical for neural shaping (Kolb, 2011), making early intervention crucial for acquiring social and communication skills. Early intervention promotes attention and increases motivation for social interactions, mitigating the effects on brain development and improving IQ, language, and adaptive behavior in children with ASD. However, the age of infants may affect the effectiveness of the intervention, as they may be unable to perform basic computer or mobile device operations. There is a significant disparity in IQ among individuals with ASD; approximately 50% are estimated to have intellectual disabilities, and the association between ASD and intellectual disability varies across regions and ages (Lord et al., 2018). Children under six years of age generally exhibit higher mean IQ scores than older children do, and both nonverbal and verbal IQs exhibit a U-shaped distribution with age (Al-Mamari et al., 2021). Patients with higher IQs typically show better understanding and mastery of tasks in VR therapy, with more active participation during treatment. In contrast, individuals with lower IQs may encounter greater challenges in task execution, situational comprehension, and skill application.

Interventions lasting less than 30 minutes are more effective for improving social and affective skills. Longer sessions may cause motion sickness or anxiety in children, which can reduce the effectiveness of the intervention (Malihi et al., 2020). Regarding intervention frequency, research

indicates that social skill improvement interventions are most effective when conducted no more than three times per week. For example, (McCleery et al., 2020) suggest that IVR can be administered up to three times per week. Regarding the intervention period, a duration of 10-20 weeks is recommended for improving social skills. Theoretically, prolonged interventions are expected to yield better results, as humans typically require extended periods of focused practice to acquire and maintain complex skills. However, it is important to note that excessively prolonged interventions may result in diminishing returns due to cognitive fatigue and the lengthy nature of the intervention.

4.4. Brain Activation Mechanism of VR Technology Intervention in ASD

Although VR technology has been widely applied in the treatment of ASD, its exact mechanisms of action remain incompletely understood. To date, few studies, both domestically and internationally, have explored the neural mechanisms underlying the behavioral improvements observed in ASD patients after VR-based interventions.

During semantic processing, ASD patients consistently activate typical brain regions involved in language processing, such as the left inferior frontal and inferior temporal gyri. However, compared with typical populations, ASD patients display a distinct pattern of brain activation differences characterized by insufficient activation of typical brain areas, especially within the left frontal lobe (Yu et al., 2022). By utilizing neuroimaging techniques, such as magnetic resonance imaging, to track brain response changes in children with ASD, it is possible to evaluate the effectiveness of VR-based interventions from the perspective of neural plasticity and uncover the neural basis for behavioral changes. For instance, (Yang et al., 2018) employed a validated biological motion fMRI task to measure changes in brain blood oxygen level-dependent signals before and after VR intervention, identifying functional activity alterations in

three key brain regions. First, the right posterior superior temporal sulcus, a critical hub for social cognitive processing, showed significant increases in activation when exposed to social stimuli, especially in individuals who exhibited more substantial improvements in Theory of Mind tasks. This brain region plays a crucial role in the multisensory integration and processing of social information, providing a neural foundation for interpreting others' intentions. Second, the left inferior frontal gyrus, a vital area for socioemotional processing, demonstrated a close correlation with improvements in emotion recognition. Compared with nonsocial stimuli, this area showed reduced activation in response to social stimuli. This may indicate that VR-SCT helps shift emotional processing from language-centered strategies to those more suited for emotion recognition. Finally, the left parietal operculum, which is primarily involved in visual attention, showed significantly lower activation in response to nonsocial stimuli than to social stimuli across all participants. This suggests a shift in visual attention from nonsocial to social cues, a crucial indicator of improved social functioning in ASD patients. These findings underscore the significant role of the right posterior superior temporal sulcus in enhancing theory of mind and the critical contributions of the left inferior frontal gyrus and parietal operculum to emotion recognition and attentional shifts. These results provide strong scientific support for the continued use of VR technology in ASD treatment.

4.5. Challenges of VR Technology in ASD

Safety risks, both physical and psychological, may be associated with the use of VR. Motion sickness, commonly experienced in VR, manifests as fatigue, discomfort, dizziness, and can induce symptoms such as eye strain, nausea, and disorientation (Oh & Lee, 2021). Psychologically, individuals with ASD typically exhibit heightened sensory sensitivity, especially to visual and auditory stimuli

(Ringold et al., 2022). VR headsets and headphones can trigger discomfort or excessive sensory stimulation, resulting in anxiety, nausea, or unease. In highly immersive VR environments, the weight of the equipment, screen flickering, sound variations, or sudden visual input can negatively affect individuals with ASD (Madary & Metzinger, 2016). Additionally, the high prevalence of tactile hypersensitivity in children with ASD presents a significant barrier to the application of VR technology in research, diagnosis, and treatment. For example, during interventions, some children with ASD may resist wearing headsets, closing their eyes, or repeatedly remove them, disrupting the intervention process. Attention deficits in children with ASD, characterized by poor focus and sustained attention, often manifest as difficulties in tasks requiring prolonged concentration. This may lead to behaviors such as withdrawal, passivity, or irritability when faced with tasks requiring sustained attention and longer durations. Moreover, certain training activities in current VR interventions are poorly designed, particularly those involving repetitive and monotonous exercises, which, once novelty wears off, may result in boredom in children with ASD (Lei Fan; Yangsong Du; Guangtao Zhai, 2018). The higher cost and greater technological dependence of VR treatments, compared to traditional treatments, requiring specialized equipment and technical support, may limit access for many individuals.

To address these limitations, improvements in equipment design to enhance comfort should be considered. For instance, using soft materials and adjustable headbands could reduce the physical burden of the devices. Additionally, non-contact technologies or more flexible wearable options offer effective solutions. For example, eye-tracking or gesture recognition technologies can eliminate the need for headsets, thereby alleviating discomfort. Gradual adaptation strategies are a promising approach, where patients are gradually introduced to device usage, starting with short periods, and progressively increasing

the duration. This approach not only reduces discomfort and anxiety but also facilitates smoother integration of patients into the technological intervention process (Lei Fan; Yangsong Du;Guangtao Zhai, 2018; M. Zhang et al., 2022).

4.6. *Limitations*

The specific forms of VR interventions, including the equipment used, as well as the duration, frequency, and timing, vary considerably. Furthermore, the assessment tools made it difficult to directly compare the effects of the interventions across studies. The substantial heterogeneity of the studies included may have affected the uniformity and comparability of the results. It is essential to acknowledge the considerable individual variability in symptom expression among individuals with autism. Consequently, the effectiveness of VR interventions may vary for people with ASDs of different severities. One limitation is that the present study did not thoroughly explore the potential effect of these individual differences on the outcomes. Notably, existing studies have focused predominantly on short-term effects within the intervention period. Few studies have addressed the long-term effects of VR interventions for individuals with ASD, an area that warrants further exploration.

4.7. *Future research*

VR interventions are available in various forms and devices, and it is crucial for future research to explore the effect of different intervention options on skill development in individuals with ASD. For example, comparing the suitability of semi-immersive and fully immersive devices for different populations, as well as investigating the efficacy of combining VR with other intervention methods, is necessary. Additionally, individual patient differences, such as age, gender, and disease level, should be considered. Studies should also investigate the neural mechanisms underlying VR interventions for

individuals with ASD. The application of brain imaging techniques (e.g., fMRI, EEG) could help determine whether VR interventions improve social cognition, emotional processing, and other areas by altering neural activation patterns. A comprehensive investigation into the brain-modulating effects of VR interventions would provide stronger scientific support for their use. Moreover, studying specific timeframes (e.g., frequency, duration, and periodicity) could contribute to the development of optimal intervention programs for diverse populations.

5. Conclusion

In general, VR technology effectively enhances social, affective, daily living, and cognitive skills in individuals with ASD. Our study suggests that early interventions targeting social skills should involve fully immersive VR equipment, limited to no more than three 30-minute sessions per week, lasting between 10 and 20 weeks. Similarly, interventions targeting affective skills should also be limited to approximately 30 minutes per session.

6. Ethics approval and consent to participate

Not acceptable.

Competing interests

None.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

***: Writing - original draft, Data curation, Conceptualization, Methodology. ***: Writing - review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. ***: Writing - original draft, Data curation.

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Table 1

Characteristics of the included studies.

Author, year	Sample Size (Female %)	Age (Mean/ Range, yrs)	Diagnostic methods	Intervention Type	Intervention Method	Intervention Content	Control Group Intervention Content
(Sosnowski et al., 2022)	54(12.96)	4-14	Not reported	VR Emotion Recognition Training	Emotion recognition training based on 3D immersive video games	The game uses auditory and visual cues (including stimuli and responses) to encourage players to focus on specific facial emotional expression areas	Video game
(Frolli et al., 2022)	60(15)	9-10	DSM-V	VR Emotion Recognition Training	Emotion and context recognition training based on VR 3D projection	The projection shows basic emotions (e.g., happiness, sadness, anger) and secondary emotions (e.g., pride, shame, guilt), along with specific scenarios where these emotions occur	Therapist intervention
(Genova et al., 2024)	14(7.14)	16-19	Not reported	Standard Special Education Pre-Employment Transition Services + VR Interview Training	VR-based simulated job interview	Participants select a job (e.g., cashier, food service, security guard, office clerk) and respond to questions posed by researchers	Standard Special Education Pre-Employment Transition Services

Author, year	Sample Size (Female %)	Age (Mean/ Range, yrs)	Diagnostic methods	Intervention Type	Intervention Method	Intervention Content	Control Group Intervention Content
(Ji & Yang, 2021)	67(43.28)	12.9	Not reported	VR Visual Attention Training	FIFA21 game	Football game in a VR environment	Psychological counseling
(Y. Wang et al., 2016)	70(15.71)	4.07	DSM-IV	Traditional Behavioral Training + VR Training	VR-based digital audio-visual integration therapy system	Use of bio sounding dolphin high-frequency sounds in a virtual ocean scenario combined with digital audio-visual integration technology for ASD child treatment	Traditional Behavioral Training
(Maskey et al., 2019)	32(21.88)	8-14	DSM-IV	VR Relaxation Training	Relaxation and breathing training in VR stress and fear scenarios	Personalized settings based on children's fear of objects and intensity, e.g., children afraid of dogs practice relaxation in scenarios featuring dogs	Conventional therapy
(Smith et al., 2021)	71(18.31)	16-26	Not reported	Conventional Services + VR Interview Training	VR-based simulated job interview	Responding to interview questions in a VR environment	Conventional therapy
(Smith et al., 2014)	26(23.08)	18-31	Not reported	VR Interview Training	VR-based simulated job interview	Responding to interview questions in a VR environment	Conventional therapy
(J. Zhao & Zhang, 2021)	114(unclear)	3-5	DSM-V	Home Rehabilitation Nursing + VR Training	VR-based simulated video game	Children wear helmets and hold controllers to engage in rehabilitation interventions via virtual game scenarios,	Home Rehabilitation Nursing

Author, year	Sample Size (Female %)	Age (Mean/ Range, yrs)	Diagnostic methods	Intervention Type	Intervention Method	Intervention Content	Control Group Intervention Content
						interacting with animated characters to promote verbal expression	
(J. Zhao et al., 2022)	44(20.46)	3-6	DSM-V	VR Training	VR-based video game	In the virtual environment, patients are instructed to place the cursor on targets or respond to questions based on virtual characters' cues in different scenarios	Conventional therapy
(Ip et al., 2018)	72 (11.11)	9	Not reported	VR Emotional Skills Training	VR-based emotion and social adaptation skills training	Developed six unique scenarios, including experiencing the four seasons in a VR environment and interacting with virtual objects. A calm environment is provided to help children settle down during emotional outbursts, etc.	Conventional therapy
(White et al., 2016)	8 (unclear)	20.5	Not reported	VR Social Interaction Skills Training	VR-based game application for social interaction skills training	In a classroom scene, participants greet other students (virtual agents), initiate conversations, ask questions, and interact in the virtual environment	CLS Psychosocial Intervention
(X. Zhang & Zhao, 2022)	66 (21.21)	5	DSM-V	VR Cognitive Training	VR-based cognitive rehabilitation care	Using Unity3D, a VR training project was developed to help ASD children rehabilitate, with six training scenarios (e.g., finding a backpack, map, banana)	Conventional therapy

Author, year	Sample Size (Female %)	Age (Mean/ Range, yrs)	Diagnostic methods	Intervention Type	Intervention Method	Intervention Content	Control Group Intervention Content
(Genova et al., 2024)	20 (75)	19.35	DSM-V	VR Interview Training	interviewing practice with a virtual human	For each virtual interview, trainees selected one of fourteen jobs (e.g., cashier, clerical, customer service) that guided the virtual interview experience. Then, trainees interviewed virtual hiring managers by answering their questions.	Conventional therapy
(He et al., 2021)	12 (unclear)	6-9	Not reported	VR Training	Auxiliary treatment system of childhood autism based on VR	Through multiple training scenarios and using behavior tree decision technology to process the intelligent decision-making of the role, the child can interact with the role and complete tasks in the present situation	Conventional therapy
(Sepehri Bonab et al., 2024)	40 (unclear)	8.92	DSM-V	VR Emotional Skills Training	VR game	Four common Kinect sports games (baseball, basketball, bowling, and football) were used in the gaming room for this purpose. The chosen games aimed to challenge and enhance various fundamental motor skills in participants, encompassing the ability to manipulate	Conventional therapy

Author, year	Sample Size (Female %)	Age (Mean/ Range, yrs)	Diagnostic methods	Intervention Type	Intervention Method	Intervention Content	Control Group Intervention Content
(Sun, 2019)	16 (25)	6-9	DSM-V	VR Emotional Skills Training	Intervention system for social-emotional skills in children with autism based on VR technology	and control objects through underhand and overhand throwing, striking, dribbling, catching, and kicking. Using a virtual dolphin character to interact with children with autism, guiding them to complete game tasks in pre-set scenarios	Conventional therapy
(Wu, 2023)	44 (unclear)	4-8	DSM-V	VR Training	Systematic VR scenario training	The entire training process is connected by a storyline, where at the beginning, an intelligent character informs children with autism that they need to embark on a trip to visit a friend	Conventional therapy
(S. Zhao, 2022)	76 (43.4)	4.58	DSM-V	VR Training + Applied behavior analysis	Dolphin house digital bionic training system	Dolphin House digital bionic training system intervention therapy. Irregular frequency modulation delivers digital bionic dolphin high-frequency sound in the range of 20,000 to 80,000 Hz, combined with specially designed digital-controlled lighting and multimedia	Applied behavior analysis

Author, year	Sample Size (Female %)	Age (Mean/ Range, yrs)	Diagnostic methods	Intervention Type	Intervention Method	Intervention Content	Control Group Intervention Content
						ocean background videos for visual stimulation	
(Ambrose, 2022)	12 (16.6)	14.87	Not reported	VR Training	Open simulator virtual environment	Role-playing in a virtual environment	Conventional therapy

Fig. 1.	PRISMA flow diagram for literature search and selection process.
Fig. 2.	Forest plot of meta-analyses